

4Q104 (4QRuth^a) frag. 2 (PAM 43.689 frag. 2)

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In 2000, Eugene Ulrich and Catherine M. Murphy jointly published the two Qumran Cave 4 Ruth manuscripts. The largest, 4Q104, consists of several pieces joined together to form one fragment preserving part of Ruth 1:1-12. The editors characterized the script as late Hasmonaean (I consider it to be later, early to middle Herodian), transcribed the text on the fragment, listed the orthographic variants vis-à-vis the Masoretic text and 4Q105, and listed the textual variants, including two cases where 4Q104 goes against the Masoretic text. The observations of the edition have been summarized in the scant subsequent scholarship, but without any further discussion.

The editors correctly observed that the first seven lines contain less letter-spaces per line than the subsequent ones. This may in part be due to the somewhat larger size of the letters in the first six or seven lines, though it is difficult to judge from the photographs whether the bottom part of the fragment might have shrunk, thus giving the impression of smaller letters. A demonstrable reason for the increasing amount of letters per line is the slanting right margin. Overall, the scribe began most new lines slightly more towards the right than the preceding one, so that accordingly more letter-spaces would fit in the lines (the *waw* at the very beginning of line 12 may have been a secondary addition after the scribe started at the margin with תשאנה). A precise reconstruction of the words at the right side of the fragment is not possible. The scribe was inconsistent, with respect to the spacing between letters and between words.

One small fragment (PAM 43.689 frag. 2), hitherto unidentified, should be added to 4Q104 at the right of lines 9-10 (Ruth 1:7-8) where it attests to two more variants. Although no entire word is preserved on the fragment, its identification is assured by the combination of textual, palaeographic, and material features. Both the bottom and the top left of the newly identified fragment may join the main 4Q104 fragment, if one allows for some shrinkage of the bottom part of

4Q104. I present here 4Q104 lines 8-11 (Ruth 1:6-9) with the new fragment (highlighted in red ink) and a different arrangement of the words in the lines.

[שמעה ב]שדה מואב כי פקד יהוה ⁷ את עמו לתת להם לחם ⁷ ותצא מן המקום אשר]	8
[ה]ת ⁸ שם ⁸ [וש]תי כלותיה עמה ⁸ [ותלכנה בדרך לשוב אל ארץ יהודה ⁸ ותאמר נעמי]	9
[לשתי [כלותי]ה [לכנה שבנה א]שה לבית אמה יעש יהוה עמכם חסד כאשר עשיתם]	10
[עם המ]תים ועמדי ⁹ [יתן יהוה לכם ומצאן מנוחה אשה בית אישה ותשק להן]	11

Comments on Reading

Materially the fragment might actually join to the main fragment (as show in the figure below). Textually, one might prefer to position the fragment a few millimetres more to the right.

In line 9 (line 1 of the newly identified fragment) the *taw* is certain, and the *shin* virtually certain, even though most of the *shin* has been abraded. The few remains after *shin* strongly are more compatible with final *mem*, then which medial *mem*. The remaining vertical stroke right to *taw*, at the edge of the fragment is impossible to identify. If this reading is correct, we have two variants vis-à-vis the Masoretic text. The variant couple שם/שמה is common in manuscripts, but ת⁸[ה would be a rare orthographic variant for היתה (see the *ketiv* reading in 2 Kings 9:37). Or one might even have an entirely different variant word ending in *taw*. In line 10 (line 2 of the newly identified fragment) probably the only variant is the full writing with *waw* of כלותיה, as also in line 9, rather than the defective writing without *waw*, כלתוה, in the Masoretic text. Note, however, that the *he* of כלותיה is missing in the join, and would only fit if we place the fragment more to the right, or assume no space between כלותיה and לכנה.

Because a precise reconstruction of the right part of the joint fragments is not possible due to the above-mentioned scribal irregularities and apparent shrinking of the material, the textual restoration of the lines is uncertain. For example, the word לשתי seems too long for the beginning

of line 10, but perhaps this manuscripts read a variant **אל שתי**, with **אל** at the end of line 9 and **שתי** at the beginning.

Join of 4Q104 frag. 1 (IAA Plate 410, frag. 2) and frag. 2 (PAM 43.689 frag. 2; IAA Plate 90, frag. 8);

Courtesy of the Israel Antiquities Authority, photographs Shai Halevi

